

DESTINATION EARTH CO-DESIGN TOOLKIT

Worksheet 1

Approaching users and the user monitoring
framework

December 2025

Funded by
the European Union

Destination Earth

implemented by

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document constitutes the Essential Worksheet #1 “User Monitoring Framework”. It focuses on the first phase of the co-design process, which relies on identifying and liaising with potential users. The User Monitoring Framework focuses on establishing resilient relationships with promising potential users, for building, and launching joint co-design activities with them. As such, eventually, this framework is intended to be used by service providers for engaging in co-design activities with potential end-users during the initial stages of service design.

Two complementary streams of activities that can be performed to engage and monitor users in the earliest phase of co-design, which are covered by the User Monitoring Framework:

- 1) A preliminary diagnosis based on public reports can help to structure a consistent knowledge base about users' needs, skills (in particular design skills) and challenges.
- 2) The initiation of the relationship with users can be managed through a series of steps aimed at gradually building a solid basis for collaboration.

The Worksheet first introduces the process and toolchain that would support service providers in identifying, selecting and engaging promising users in order to build a strong, resilient co-design relationship.

After providing some critical recalls on the co-design methods, this document introduces the step-by-step process for user approach, then, it introduces and clarifies the relationship between the process for user approach and the toolchain.

Table of contents

- 1. Introduction to the User Approach Phase 3**
 - 1.1. Introduction to the Phase #1 – Approaching users..... 3
 - 1.2. Position of the User Monitoring framework within the toolchain 3
 - 1.3. Objectives 6
- 2. A step-by-step process for approaching users..... 7**
 - 2.1. Step #1: Performing a preliminary diagnosis of the potential use ecosystem to build a consistent initial knowledge base 8
 - 2.2. Step #2: Identification of potential users..... 11
 - 2.3. Step #3: User Approach 12
 - 2.4. Step #4: Initial User Engagement..... 13
- 3. The User Monitoring Framework as a set of tools to support User Approach..... 14**
 - 3.1. The ID Cards 14
 - 3.1.1. Stakeholder ID Cards 15
 - 3.1.2. Project ID Cards 16
 - 3.2. Assessment radars..... 17
 - 3.2.1. Stakeholder assessment radar 17
 - 3.2.2. Project assessment radar 19
 - 3.3. Ecosystem mapping 21
- 4. Recommended use of the User Monitoring Framework..... 22**

1. Introduction to the User Approach Phase

1.1. Introduction to the Phase #1 – Approaching users

The first phase in the co-design process is the user approach. It consists in identifying, approaching and engaging with promising potential users. Crossing the “Grand Distance”¹ between service providers and their potential users stands as a critical challenge to take up in this phase.

Grand Distance refers to the fact that potential users usually misunderstand or are not even aware of the potential value of services based on DestinE data. Conversely, DestinE service providers may not always have a full understanding of the specific needs of users or a clear picture of who the potential users might be. Consequently, approaching users constitutes the very first step in connecting service providers with various potential use ecosystems to establish a mutual learning dynamic. However, Grand Distance unfolds into a variety of dimensions, which makes the dialogue between users and service providers considerably more complex:

- **Cognitive:** they can have different understandings of their challenges, so they should build a common ground of understanding
- **Social:** they can have different culture and social practices that could lead to misunderstandings
- **Organizational:** they should cross the borders of their respective organizations, and to adapt to new processes and ways of working
- **Institutional:** they can adhere to “dissimilar or different regimes of rules, norms or conventions” which hamper their ability to collaborate
- **Geographical:** they can be located in different countries or even continents.

To overcome this complexity and foster the emergence of a space for constructive dialogue between service providers and various potential users, this worksheet proposes a progressive, step by step process to approach consistent user and monitor their engagement using a User Monitoring Framework.

The following document outlines a step-by-step process for progressively engaging potential users, along with tools to establish and continuously update a comprehensive knowledge base using the User Monitoring Framework. It also examines how this knowledge base can be effectively leveraged to support the various stages of the user approach.

1.2. Position of the User Monitoring framework within the toolchain

The User Monitoring Framework constitutes the entry point in the process of co-design. As such, its outcomes feed the ‘Data-Information-Value’ Framework used in the diagnosis phase (phase 2 of the co-design process).

The full description of the co-design process is introduced in *Worksheet 0 “Destination Earth Co-design toolkit. Introduction and overview of the co-design methods.”*

¹ “Grand distance”: a situation where actors have no obvious way to interact since they show a high degree of distance on many dimensions e.g. cognitive, organizational, geographical, institutional, social.

1.3. Objectives

The process of user approach and the User Monitoring Framework are intended to provide service providers with consistent methods and tools to launch and monitor co-design activities. Their objectives are to support both:

- The structuring and update of a consistent knowledge base about potential usage.
- The progressive establishment of strong working relationships with potential users, from the preliminary diagnosis of the potential use ecosystems to an effective engagement of users.

Building a strong knowledge base about potential use ecosystems is particularly critical to set the ground to co-design relationships based on a resilient-fit perspective. It aims at increasing chances of success by opening various alternatives in a diversity of contexts. Following this perspective, structuring a consistent initial knowledge base can help:

1. Avoid fixations² on who users are and their needs.
2. Develop a clear and cohesive vision that is transparent and consistently communicated across the entire team and stakeholders involved in co-design activities.
3. Disentangle complex usage ecosystems to anticipate needs, elaborate a relevant positioning and establish robust relationships.
4. Identify several potential users and alternative action plans instead of focusing on a single user.

² A fixation effect occurs when one idea or perspective (usually based on known existing solutions) monopolizes attention and slows down the search for original alternative solutions.

2.A step-by-step process for approaching users

Approaching users should be understood as a progressive process focused on staging a fertile ground for interactions and collaborative work. Its key goals are to establish visibility and trust, while simultaneously gaining insights from their perspectives and needs, creating a foundation for collaborative working relationships. This process starts based on the preliminary diagnosis of the usage ecosystem and should end up supporting a consistent diagnosis of the co-design needs.

It can be broken down into four main steps that support a progressive path from the coarse understanding of complex use ecosystems towards the initialization of co-design relationships with engaged users. These steps are discussed below and represented in Figure 2.

Figure 2. The key Steps of Approaching Users

CRITICAL INSIGHT: the interest of considering a ‘co-design opportunity backlog’ aside from the main co-design pipeline

Throughout the process, various stakeholders can be identified. However, some may not initially participate in a co-design initiative due to a lack of immediate interest or challenges in establishing engagement.

Over time, their perspectives and objectives may shift, potentially leading to an interest in collaborating on co-design initiatives in the future. Therefore, it is advisable to view these stakeholders as part of a "co-design opportunity backlog" rather than disregarding them entirely.

2.1. Step #1: Performing a preliminary diagnosis of the potential use ecosystem to build a consistent initial knowledge base

The goal of the preliminary diagnosis is to build an initial understanding of the targeted usage ecosystem, to identify a variety of potential users to be approached. As such, it relies on structuring a comprehensive knowledge base regarding potential users, their projects and relationships within the use ecosystem and the ways in which DestinE services could help them to reach their objectives. This method applies at local, regional, national and trans-national scales, and to public, private and civil-society users; in what follows, local authorities are used as an example to illustrate concrete actions.

Documentary searches based on public and private reports constitute a good strategy to perform a quick preliminary diagnosis and initialize a relatively dense knowledge base regarding potential usage ecosystems. The websites of the potential users constitute a convenient starting point for such documentary search. In practice, a user monitoring framework is introduced in this worksheet (section 3) to support these searches and systematically gather relevant information, by scanning official portals, open-data catalogs and recent project pages.

In the case of complex ecosystems, such as those in which public decision-makers operate, structuring a consistent knowledge base is essential to understand the challenges encountered by potential users, their ambitions, their levers for action and their potential needs. It is also necessary to identify their competencies, particularly in terms of design, in order to clarify the nature of the dependencies between the stakeholders that could be involved in the co-design process as well as potential path for collaboration. A short “map” of who decides what (mandates, budgets, timelines) at the relevant scale greatly accelerates this step and prevents outreach to the wrong teams.

In that sense this initial knowledge base and the preliminary diagnosis allow to clarify the co-design landscape. In particular, such a preliminary diagnosis should be performed to:

- Identify potential co-design themes that fit with both the service provider’s expertise and the specific concerns of the stakeholders engaged in the targeted use ecosystem
- Map the ecosystem of stakeholders that could be engaged in co-design activities and identify their key concerns and competencies
- Identify potential users to be approached as to launch the co-design initiative, but also potential partners, prescriber or other third parties that should be involved in the co-design process
- Build a consistent contact backlog to leverage the ecosystem as new needs, challenges or opportunities emerge throughout the co-design journey

When structured effectively, this knowledge base can be continually updated as co-design processes progress, new stakeholders are identified, and fresh opportunities arise.

To reach these objectives and focus on the relevant information required during this preliminary diagnosis, this worksheet introduces three simple tools (see section 3): 1) the ID Cards to gather and store information about ecosystem stakeholders and projects; 2) the assessment radars to evaluate the interest of the various stakeholders and projects identified; 3) the ecosystem mapping method, to build a consolidated understanding of the relationships between stakeholders within the targeted use ecosystem. Altogether, these tools constitute a User monitoring framework that supports the initialization and continuous update of a consistent knowledge base. The section 3 of this worksheet provides clear guidance on how to use these complementary tools to perform a preliminary diagnosis, but also to support the entire process of approaching users.

Also, the following frame gives a concrete example of how to build a consistent knowledge base in a context where local authorities are targeted as potential users.

Building a consistent knowledge base: the case of local authorities as potential users

In line with the objectives of co-design activities, and focusing on local authorities as potential users, a generic structure for the initial knowledge base is proposed, built around four types of information (figure 3). These four types of information are equally important to assess the potential needs for DestinE services and potential co-design opportunities in the context of local authorities. The same four types apply to regional, national and trans-national contexts: only the institutions and document sources change.

Figure 3. Proposed dimensions for the initial knowledge base built during the preliminary diagnosis

a) Key specificities of the territory

The first dimension of the knowledge base focuses on the geographic features of the territory. It emphasizes the importance of understanding the distinct characteristics of the areas where these services will be implemented.

A knowledge base can be built up on this subject during the preliminary diagnostic phase. In the example of addressing local authorities, it implies to collect different categories of information:

1. The geographic footprint and structure of the territory: start by defining the perimeter and how the area is organized (this frames everything that follows).
2. Natural characteristics of the territory (topographic profile; protected/sensitive ecosystems or biodiversity, green/blue corridors, etc.): establish the physical and ecological baseline that constrains/enables use.
3. Human activities (the nature of key economic activities, main economic zones, density of population, etc.): then situate people and activities within that physical context.
4. The main risk factors on the territory (e.g. fire, flooding, tectonic): finally, identify risks as the result of geography + natural characteristics + human activities (i.e., exposure and vulnerability depend on the first three).

Such information is critical for identifying the relevant themes that may be interesting to address through co-design and DestinE data.

b) Organization of local authorities

Supporting policymakers is one of the objectives of DestinE. Consequently, local authorities emerge as pivotal potential users in the development of DestinE-based services. Therefore, an important goal of the preliminary diagnosis is to understand their needs, challenges, actions and plans. Building such an understanding entails gathering various types of information:

- Information on the organization of the various local authorities, their scope of action e.g., **France**: Region, Department, Metropolitan Area, Municipality; **Germany**: Land, Kreis, Gemeinde; **Spain**: Comunidad Autónoma, Provincia, Municipio; **Italy**: Regione, Provincia/Città Metropolitana.), their respective domain of responsibility (e.g., promotion of renewable energies and energy efficiency, preservation of the environment and resources, urban planning and mobility, education, energy, water, infrastructure, etc.) and their relationships.
- Information on the key policies and action plans deployed by these various local authorities (e.g. plans related to mobility, water pollution, urban air quality, low carbon strategy, clean energy strategy, smart cities).
- Information regarding local representatives, including their roles and contact information. Usually, they can be easily accessed through the organizational charts of local authorities.

This information is consistent for comprehending which stakeholders are most relevant to the domains that DestinE can help address. It is also critically relevant when it comes to understanding the needs, challenges, and objectives of the local policymakers as well as to identifying promising contact points.

c) Key local stakeholders and their competencies

The third aspect of this knowledge base focuses on the stakeholders involved in local activities related to environmental matters. These stakeholders can be of various profiles including (but not limited to):

- Private local stakeholders working for/with local authorities, or not.
- Public or private stakeholders involved in local innovation projects.
- Local research laboratories.
- Local unions involved in territory management.
- Associations acting as prescribing bodies on environmental issues.

Involving various stakeholders in the co-design process is generally beneficial and, depending on the context, may be necessary. Whether it is beneficial or mandatory depends on the co-design objectives, the governance setting, and the roles these stakeholders play in the targeted ecosystem. For each of these stakeholders, information regarding their competencies can be collected to assess their potential as users and/or partner. In particular, four key dimensions can be assessed to understand their profile:

- **Competencies regarding data**, including: their ability to collect and store data; their ability to analyze data; their main use of data; the type of data they are used to handle.
- **Their relationships with local authorities**, including their involvement in local innovation projects involving public authorities; their contracts with local authorities; the public funding they receive, etc.
- **Their orientation towards environmental issues**, including involvement in projects related to air quality, water quality, land monitoring or renewable energies for instance.
- **Their design competencies**, as to assess their capabilities to engage and collaborate in complex innovation project such as those focused on DestinE service development

This information is critical to assess the relationships within the local ecosystem as well as to estimate the variety of potential users and partners. An important point to keep in mind is that every stakeholder involved in a local project could stand as a potential user and/or partner in

the process. This supports the resiliency of the co-design approach, as you design a portfolio of contacts, entry points, and collaboration avenues that can be activated as contexts evolve.

d) Key local projects

The fourth dimension of the initial knowledge base focuses on the local innovation projects related to DestinE data-based services and/or sustainability. For each of these projects, a bundle of generic information can be easily collected:

- The type of project (public/private, research/operational, TRL, etc.)
- The goal of the project and expected results
- The funding sources (including amounts when available)
- The list of stakeholders and their role within the project (when available)
- The timeline of the project

This information is important since nowadays many public authorities are already leading transition towards sustainability. Understanding local initiatives can help positioning services based on DestinE data within this local transition. It implies collecting information about achieved, ongoing and planned projects involving local actors around sustainability issues. This list is not exhaustive and may be complemented with additional information when deemed necessary and useful to the context.

2.2. Step #2: Identification of potential users

The second step relates to the identification of potential users. Here, the objective is to identify users who can perceive value in the use of DestinE data and who can be mobilized to build a working relationship. Such users can be identified based on the preliminary diagnosis of the usage ecosystem since much of the information collected can represent meaningful insights to assess the potential of a given stakeholder as a user:

- The involvement of each stakeholder in innovation projects: It informs on their openness to collaboration and the nature of the projects they are interested in.
- The preliminary analysis of the competencies of each actor: it informs on their ability to handle DestinE services and the extent to which they could have to be (in)formed about DestinE data and its potential. This includes the dimensions already defined in the worksheet (e.g., competencies regarding data and Earth Observation, thematic scientific/operational competencies, relationships with public authorities, orientation towards environmental issues, and design competencies).
- Their role and mandate in relation to policies and action plans: who is responsible for the relevant themes and decisions, and at which scale (local, regional, national, trans-national).
- Timelines of policies and projects: alignment with upcoming windows (e.g., plan updates, project milestones) where co-design work could be inserted.
- Position in the ecosystem: connections to other stakeholders and projects identified during the preliminary diagnosis, which can facilitate collaboration and open additional avenues.
- Etc.

Identification is progressive: not all stakeholders and users will enter the process at the beginning. As the knowledge base is updated (through Steps #3 and #4), new actors may appear and previously identified actors may become relevant. Stakeholders who are not ready immediately should be kept in a co-design opportunity backlog and re-visited as contexts, projects, and priorities evolve. This dynamic intake supports a resilient approach by maintaining multiple potential pathways toward engagement.

CRITICAL INSIGHT

Previous research on co-design highlights the significant gap that often exists between service providers and their users. To address this, it is recommended to identify a diverse pool of potential users rather than focusing narrowly on a single user. Engaging with multiple stakeholders increases the likelihood of finding successful collaborations and fosters a more adaptable approach. This strategy aligns with the 'resilient-fit' perspective on co-design, which emphasizes flexibility and resilience in building productive relationships with users.

2.3. Step #3: User Approach

The objective is to engage with the potential users to stimulate their interest and initiate a potential relationship. The initial contact should be followed by a formal meeting to clarify the co-design initiative and to envision potential collaborative paths.

A first objective for this initial relationship is to create interest by illustrating potential uses relevant to the users own specific activities. A second objective is to confirm the preliminary diagnosis. The first formal encounter should initiate a dynamic of reciprocal learning setting the ground for resilient relationships.

Although this initial meeting is not a co-design workshop per se, a few best practices should be observed to maximize the interest of potential users and lay fertile ground for a potential co-design relationship. These best practices include:

1. **Adapting the narrative to the interlocutor:** In most cases, the potential users will not be experts in data management, software engineering, modelling workflows, or result interpretation, amongst other technical areas. But the preliminary diagnosis on user competencies could help to unveil their level of knowledge in these fields as well as their own specific expertise. The narrative should be adapted to the user's level of proficiency and its own expertise, in order to ensure the core objectives and interests of the potential collaboration are well understood.
2. **Showcasing prototypes:** Showcasing prototypes could help non-expert users in projecting themselves into potential uses and to understand the value of DestinE-based services that could be co-designed. To maximize these effects, it is preferable to focus the showcase on case studies rather than on technical elements related to service operation. Also, to avoid fixation effects² by the users, it is preferable to focus on the perspectives and potential of a future service rather than on its current capabilities.
3. **Encouraging potential users to share their perspectives:** Co-design builds the understanding users' challenges and, on the way, DestinE can help face them. This ambition must be kept as a guideline when approaching users, refraining from imposing existing solutions. With this in mind, initial discussions should enable users to detail their issues and practices, in order to enrich the initial knowledge base.
4. **Overcoming technical matters to avoid the 'so what?' effect:** At this stage, it is as important to discuss and agree on potential collaborative paths rather than exclusively discussing technology and value of the potential service. This implies preserving substantial time to address key questions such as
 - *'What kind of resources could be allocated to the co-design process and how much?'*,

- *'Who are the best contact persons in the organization to work on this project?'*, *'How could interactions be organized in the coming months?'*
- *'What other organizations might have a role to play in the co-design process?'*

It also implies to define a few concrete actions and next steps from first interactions. A typical next step should be the organization of a formal 'kick-off' gathering every person that would stand as key stakeholder for the project.

2.4. Step #4: Initial User Engagement

The fourth step relates to initial user engagement which is a critical step to launch an effective co-design process. Ideally this step takes the form of a formal 'kick-off' of the co-design initiative, which formalizes the involvement of the users within the co-design process, and agrees on:

- **The broad themes and potential uses that would be explored through the co-design process:** these must be kept broad in this first instance, since the very goals of the co-design process lies in exploring these themes and refining the potential usage based on close on-going interactions.
- **The nature of the collaborative work:** This phase clarifies the objectives, timelines and methods that would drive the collaborative work. At this stage, an evolutive agenda of the co-design relationship should be developed.
- **The type of formal engagement:** The service provider and the potential user are strongly encouraged to formalize their mutual engagement through a collaboration agreement or even a contract. Such a formal agreement is key to scale and secure the allocation of resources on both sides (including personnel, time, skills, financial investment, and other essential assets), even in cases where there is no economic compensation. When addressing key policies, such agreement constitutes a testimonial of action.

The initial user engagement lays the foundation for a relationship that should be nurtured throughout the co-design process to build a strong collaboration. The more this engagement strengthens along the course of co-design for service development, the stronger are the chances of success for the overall process and the more likely it is that other opportunities for collaboration will emerge in the future.

3. The User Monitoring Framework as a set of tools to support User Approach

The following toolchain is designed to support service providers in the process of User Approach and the structuring of their knowledge base about potential usage ecosystems. This toolkit would allow them to gather information in a structured way and to shift progressively from mostly descriptive information towards analytical knowledge that can drive their activities related to a user approach.

This toolchain includes (see figure 5):

1. **ID cards** are templates that allow to systematize data collection, focusing on meaningful information to build a structured understanding of the use ecosystem. These are mostly used to collect and store descriptive information. Two types of ID Cards are proposed:
 - **Stakeholder ID cards** can be used as a template to gather information about key actors within the ecosystem.
 - **Project ID cards** can be used as a template to gather information about key projects within the ecosystem.
2. **Assessment radars** are a way to synthesize the data collected with ID Cards through an analytical lens. They are mostly used to assess individually the stakeholders and project identified and position them in the overall usage ecosystem. Two types of assessment radars are proposed:
 - **Stakeholder assessment radars** can be used to assess the profile of the various ecosystem's stakeholders based on their competencies, to understand their potential positioning in relation to the co-design project (e.g. user, partner, prescriptor, etc.).
 - **Project assessment radars** can be used to assess the potential relationships between each identified project on the territory and the co-design project to be launched.
3. **Usage ecosystem mapping** is a way to position the various stakeholders and projects within the use ecosystem and to build a preliminary understanding of the relationships between stakeholders, between projects and between stakeholders and projects.

Figure 4. Chain of tools for the preliminary diagnosis

3.1. The ID Cards

“ID cards”, are used to index both the stakeholders and projects identified in the potential use ecosystem. It enriches the knowledge base. A template is proposed to systematically gather generic information about local stakeholders and projects (see figure 5).

As such, the interest of these ID cards is threefold:

1. They allow to structure the data collection process during the preliminary diagnosis to build a deep, evolving understanding of the potential usage ecosystem.
2. They allow to initialize and to maintain a monitoring while structuring a backlog of potential stakeholders to reach and/or projects to connect with, as the co-design process moves forward, and new opportunities emerge.
3. They can constitute a great base for building a shared understanding both within the service developer's team and between the various stakeholders involved in the co-design process

3.1.1. Stakeholder ID Cards

Stakeholder ID cards are a generic entry point to store and access the information about the stakeholders identified within the use ecosystem. As such, it includes both some very descriptive formal information regarding the stakeholder and some more comprehensive information regarding the profile, activities and positioning of the stakeholder (see figure 5).

Descriptive formal information corresponds to the banner on the top of the form and includes:

- The stakeholder's name.
- The type of stakeholder (eg. Private firm, local authority, NGO, etc)
- The location of the stakeholder / its postal address.
- Its website.
- Its logo
- Its potential as a user (from low to high)
- Its potential as a pilot/partner (from low to high)

The more comprehensive part of the ID card includes information that relates to the activity of the stakeholder and are subject to evolutions and enrichments:

- A description of the stakeholder's main activities.
- Its main ongoing projects.
- Its potential uses of DestinE.
- The potential contact points envisioned to engage in a co-design relationship.

Updating this information regularly allows to follow the evolution of the stakeholder and to understand how it could contribute to the co-design process.

Stakeholder Category:	Stakeholder ID Card n°	
Descriptive information		
Stakeholder 's name:		Logo:
Type of stakeholder:		
Location:		Potential as a user:
Website:		Potential as a pilot/partner:
Comprehensive information		
Main activities:		
Main projects:		
Potential uses of DestinE:		
Potential contact points:		

Figure 5. Template for Stakeholders ID Cards

3.1.2. Project ID Cards

ID cards stand as a generic entry point to store and access information about a specific identified project within the use ecosystem (and relevant to DestinE data, policies, or pathway to sustainability). As such, it includes both some descriptive information and some more comprehensive information regarding the relevance of the project to the co-design initiative and its potential contribution (see figure 6).

Descriptive information includes:

- The project name.
- The project type - including the geographical scope (local, national, European) and the nature of the project (research project, etc.).
- The key themes considered within the project.
- The project website.
- The project logo.
- Project orientation towards data (Low / High)
- Project orientation towards sustainability (Low / High)

The more comprehensive part of the ID card includes:

- Objectives and work packages
- Key actors involved within the project.
- Fundings sources.
- Elements about the timeline.
- Potential contact points.

Updated regularly, Id cards allow to follow the evolution of the project and to understand how it could contribute to the co-design process. It supports an initial understanding of the dynamics of the use ecosystem.

Project Category:	Project ID Card n°	
Descriptive information		
Project name:		Logo:
Type of project:		
Project key themes:		Data orientation:
Website:		Sustainability orientation:
Comprehensive information		
Key objectives and work packages:		
Key stakeholders involved:		
Funding sources:		
Timeline:		
Potential contact points		

Figure 6. Template for Project ID Cards

3.2. Assessment radars

“Assessment radars”, can be built for each identified stakeholder and project. Compared to “ID Cards” radars map the stakeholders’ characteristics and projects to assess their relevance regarding the co-design initiative to be launched.

3.2.1. Stakeholder assessment radar

The “stakeholder assessment radars” are built based on the information collected in the stakeholder ID Cards. **They support an initial synthetic understanding of the stakeholders’ profile based on a rating of key dimensions (see figure 7).**

A first set of dimensions relates to the orientation of the stakeholder’s activities:

- Orientation towards policy-making
- Orientation towards sustainability
- Orientation towards design and innovation

A second set of dimensions relates to the stakeholder’s competencies:

- Scientific competencies
- Technical competencies related to data and EO
- Business Competencies
- Operational competencies
- Collaborative competencies

For each of these dimensions, stakeholders are rated on a scale 1-5. Ratings are displayed as a “Radar chart”. Figure 7 introduces the generic template for stakeholder assessment radars and figure 8 provides an illustrative example of the assessment radar for two hypothetical actors with very different profiles.

Figure 7. Template for Stakeholder Assessment Radar

Figure 8. Illustrative examples of Stakeholder Assessment Radars

Typically, based on these illustrative radars:

- In this example, stakeholder 1 demonstrates strong competencies in data, scientific knowledge, and Earth observation, which align closely with those of DestinE service providers. This alignment suggests that collaboration with Stakeholder 1 may be relatively straightforward due to shared expertise and a common knowledge base. However, the potential for synergies and complementarities could be more limited, as overlapping competencies could reduce the opportunities to leverage distinct strengths and create innovative solutions.
- Stakeholder 2 exhibits relatively few overlapping competencies with typical DestinE service providers. This lack of shared expertise may present challenges in establishing collaboration, as there is less common ground to build upon. However, the limited overlap also suggests greater potential for synergies and complementarities, as Stakeholder 2 could bring unique perspectives and skills that complement those of the service providers, fostering innovative and multidimensional solutions.

3.2.2. Project assessment radar

The “Project assessment radars” can be built based on the information compiled through the project ID Cards. **They support an initial synthetic understanding of the nature and positioning of the projects based on their focus through a rating of:**

- Its orientation towards data.
- Its orientation towards Earth Observation.
- Its orientations towards sustainability and environmental issues.
- Its orientation towards design & Innovation.
- Its orientation towards commercial outcomes.
- Its orientation towards scientific outcomes
- Its orientation towards policy outcomes.

For each of these themes, the projects should be rated on a scale 1-5³, as to sketch a preliminary understanding of the nature of the project and its potential interest to co-design. The nature of the project clearly appears when the ratings are represented as a “Radar chart”. Figures 9 introduces a generic template for Project assessment radars and figure 10 gives an illustrative example of the assessment radars for two hypothetical projects with very different positioning and ambitions.

³ In future version of this worksheet, a more precise scale would be proposed as to rate the projects on these various possible orientations

Figure 9. Generic template for project assessment radar

Figure 10. Illustrative example of Project Assessment Radars

Typically, based on these illustrative radars, one could assess:

- Project 1 has a clear orientation towards data and design / innovation as well as environmental issues. But it is not oriented towards Earth observation and DestinE data. This project can therefore show interesting complementarities with the co-design initiative to be launched. It could be interesting to engage with Project 1.
- Project 2 is primarily oriented towards policy outcomes. It can benefit from co-design for *ex ante* policy design studies. Depending on its scope and advancement, DestinE data could respond to some concerns.

3.3. Ecosystem mapping

The third tool of the user monitoring toolchain is the ‘Ecosystem mapping’, that can be built to give an overview of the potential used ecosystem. While ‘ID Cards’ are intrinsically descriptive, and Assessment radars are focused on individual stakeholder/project assessment, the goal of the ecosystem mapping method relies on building an overarching understanding of the targeted use ecosystem. In other words, it means building the overall picture of how the actors are connected and how they are connected to the projects.

To do so a simple matrix can be built with the stakeholders identified in lines and the projects identified in column. Within the matrix, each stakeholder working on the different projects can then be marked (or indicating one’s contribution to the project). Thereby, clusters of stakeholders working frequently on same projects could be identified and some key stakeholders might be identified.

4. Recommended use of the User Monitoring Framework

The tools introduced by this Worksheet form the User Monitoring Framework (i.e. ID cards, radars, matrix). These should be used in a dynamic perspective and serve DestinE service providers all along their user engagement process. Figure 11 recalls the user approach, divided in four Steps and inputting the next phase of the co-design process “*Diagnosis of co-design needs*”. In this workflow:

- Step #1 “Preliminary diagnosis” is an initialization of the User Monitoring Framework.
- Steps #2, #3 and #4 are supported by the User Monitoring Framework. Conversely, the User Monitoring Framework is fed and progressively updated from user interactions.
- The regularly updated User Monitoring Framework serves as an entry point to Phase 2 of the co-design process “*Diagnosis of co-design needs*”.

Phase 2 is described by Worksheet 2: Co-design diagnosis and the Data-Information-Value Framework, part of the DestinE Co-Design Toolkit.

Figure 11. relationships between the process of User Approach and the User Monitoring Framework

About the authors

Mines Paris PSL, Centre of Management Science

The Center of Management Science of Mines Paris is a pioneering laboratory in management sciences since 1967. Its research strategy is based on three axes: 1) design activities and innovation capacities in global enterprises and production systems; 2) dynamics of trades and occupational health in innovation and service activities; 3) Institutional changes and new forms of governance (private and public) in a capitalism of innovation and sustainable development.

Pascal Le Masson

pascal.le_masson@minesparis.psl.eu
Pascal Le Masson is Professor at Mines Paris–PSL Research University, at the Center of Management Science. He created and co-head the Bauhaus for Transitions. He is a member of the National Academy of Technology of France.

Benoit Weil

benoit.weil@minesparis.psl.eu
Benoit Weil is Professor at Mines Paris–PSL Research University, at the Center of Management Science. He created and co-head the Bauhaus for Transitions. He conducts research on design theory, generativity models, and the management of the unknown.

Alexandre Azoulay

alexandre.azoulay@minesparis.psl.eu
Alexandre Azoulay is a post-doctoral researcher at the "Center of Management Science. He holds a PhD in management sciences from Université Côte d'Azur and specializes in strategic management.

Malik Terfous

malik.terfous@minesparis.psl.eu
Malik TERFOUS is a Ph.D. candidate at Mines Paris–PSL Research University, Center of Management Science. He obtained his degree in Physical Measurements and followed it with the completion of an engineering degree in Materials and Mechanics.

Raphaëlle Barbier

raphaelle.barbier@mines-paristech.fr
Raphaëlle Barbier owns a PhD in management sciences from Mines Paris PSL. Her PhD Thesis focuses on the elaboration of co-design methods for Earth Observation in the context of the e-shape Project.

Mines Paris PSL, Observation, Impact, Energy

The OIE Research Center develops research activities in the domains of renewable resources evaluation (solar, wind, ...), of meteorology for energy, of environmental impacts of energy uses, of interoperability and diffusion of information through databases and Web services. Its members are actively involved in scientific as well as institutional activities regarding Earth Observation and Climate change.

Nicolas Fichaux

nicolas.fichaux@minesparis.psl.eu
Dr Nicolas Fichaux is research engineer in ARMINES. He owns a PhD in earth observation applied to energy from MINES Paris PSL and an Executive MBA from IE Business School.

Thierry Ranchin

thierry.ranchin@minesparis.psl.eu
Prof. Thierry Ranchin is director of the Centre Observation, Impacts, Energy at MINES Paris PSL since 2013. He was the coordinator of the H2020 e-shape project (2019-2023) and is a member of the Strategic Advisory Board of Destination Earth.

Philippe Blanc

philippe.blanc@minesparis.psl.eu
Prof. Philippe BLANC is the head of the department Energy and Processes of MINES Paris - PSL and is the deputy head of the center Observation, Impacts, Energy. His background is related to signal and image processing, remote sensing, data sciences and applied mathematics.

Lionel Menard

lionel.menard@minesparis.psl.eu
Lionel Menard is a research scientist at the Center for Observation, Impacts, Energy at MINES Paris PSL. He has an in-depth knowledge of System Development LifeCycle (SDLC), management applied to Information System and Spatial Data Infrastructure.

Raphaël Jolivet

raphael.jolivet@minesparis.psl.eu
Raphaël Jolivet is a research engineer. He develops libraries and user interfaces to support research activities and showcase results. He specialized in open science and interoperable data.

Elena Magliaro

elena.magliaro@minesparis.psl.eu
Dr Elena Magliaro is research engineer at the "Centre Observation, Impacts, Energy" (OIE), of the Mines Paris PSL research laboratory. She holds a PhD in theoretical physics from Université Aix-Marseille (2009) on loop quantum gravity.

Benoît Gschwind

benoit.gschwind@minesparis.psl.eu
Dr. Benoît Gschwind owns a Ph.D. in Computer Science from MINES Paris PSL. Since 2010, he has been working as a research engineer at MINES Paris, focusing on the fields of energy and environment.

Etienne Wey

etienne.wey@gmail.com
Dr. Etienne Wey is a senior solar consultant. He owns a PhD from Mines Paris PSL and managed the SoDa solar resource assessment and scientific activity at Transvalor S.A. from 2009 to 2021.

Funded by
the European Union

Destination Earth

implemented by

